

Kiwon Lafiya a Mararraba Biyu: *Wasan Marafa* Na Abubakar Tunau Bisa Faifan Nazari.

Rilwanu Tanimu Umar

Sashen Hausa, Kwalejin Ilimi Ta Tarayya, Zariya.

Tsakure.

*Manufar wannan takarda ita ce yin nazari kan gudummuwar da marubuta wasannin kwaikwayon Hausa ke bayarwa a rayuwar yau da kullum wajen tattalin kiwon lafiyar al'umma, da ci gaban tattalin arziƙin kasa. Sannan takardar ta yi koƙarin fito da irin fasaha da hikimomin da marubucin **Wasan Marafa** ya yi amfani da su wajen bunkasa kiwon lafiya a sanadiyyar juyin zamani na samuwar asibitoci da likitoci da yadda suke tafiyar da mu'amallar rayuwarsu. A wannan takardar an nazarci kiwon lafiya a cikin **Wasan Marafa**. Masu iya magana kan ce "Lafiya Uwar Jiki...". Masana da manazarta sun ba da gudummuwarsu wajen gano irin muhimmancin kiwon lafiya a gargajiyan da kuma tasirin da zamani ya zo da shi musamman a Kasar Hausa.*

Gabatarwa.

Shi dai wasan kwaikwayo wasa ne wanda ake yinsa ko dai a rubuce ko kuma a aikace wanda yake koyi ne na wani abu. Wato faruwar wani abu ne da ya kasance ba gaskiya ba kuma ana hadawa da kwaikwayon wani abu don dai a sami ingancin isar da wani saƙo ta hanyar raha. Wasan kwaikwayo yana ɗaya daga cikin manyan rukunai uku na Adabin Hausa, sauran biyun su ne labarin zube da kuma waƙoƙi. Manazarta daban-daban sun ba da gudummuwa game da ma'anar wasan kwaikwayo. Misali, Dangambo (2008), ya ce "Wasan kwaikwayo kamar yadda sunan ya nuna, wasa ne da ake gina shi kan kwaikwayon wani labari, ko wata matsala ta rayuwa da ake son nusarwa ga jama'a. Yahaya da Dangambo, (1986) shi kuma ya bayyana ma'anar wasan kwaikwayo da cewa, "ko da jin sunansa ma, wasan kwaikwayo ya rigaya ya bayyana kansa, watau akwai alamun wasa, watau abin da yake raha, akwai kuma alamun kwaikwayo don kwatanta yadda ake yin sa don wani ya gani ko waɗansu su gane kyansa ko muninsa."

Galadanci da Wasu (1992), sun nuna cewa "Shi wasan kwaikwayo yana nufin wani irin wasa ne wanda akan shirya a aikace, ko a rubuce, don a fito da waɗansu halaye na mutane, ko tarihin aukuwar wani abu ko don a nuna yadda ake yin wani abu don masu kallo su gani, ko kuma masu karantawa su fahimta. Idan abin da ake nunawa cikin wasan mai kyau ne, za a gane, idan maras kyau ne ma za a iya ganewa."

Asalin Wasan Kwaikwayo

A tarihance, wasan kwaikwayo ya ɗauko asalinsa ne a duniya baki ɗaya ta inda ake gudanar da shi a gargajiyan. Babu kuma wanda zai iya cewa ga ranar da aka fara, sai dai an san cewa wasan kwaikwayo ɓangare ne na adabi da ya dace sosai. Akwai dalilai da ake ganin su suka haddasa samun wasan kwaikwayo. Alal misali: 'Yar'adua (2007) da Sulaiman, (2019) sun nuna cewa: "Dalili na farko shi ne wanda yake cewa an fara samun wasan kwaikwayo ne sakamakon bauta, watau irin bukukuwan da ake yi wa abin da jama'a suke bauta wa. A lokacin bukin wannan bauta ne na shekara shekara shugabannin wannan addini suke sauya kama suna kwaikwayon ɗabi'u da ke cikin wasannin da aka rubuta a gaban masu kallo."

Dalili na biyu kuma shi ne: "Wai akwai waƙoƙi da kirari da akan yi a lokacin binne jarumai, wanda yake bayanin irin halayensu na jarunta. Da kuma aka yi nisa, wani lokaci har akan samu wani ko wasu mutane masu zuwa suna kwaikwayon irin yadda waɗannan jarumai suke aiwatar da jaruntarsu ko a wurin farauta ko a wurin yaƙi."

Dalili na uku kuma shi ne: “Wai wasan kwaikwayo ya samu ne a dalilin bayar da labarin da ake wa mutane, misali a dandamali ko kuma idan an je yawon farauta, to a wannan lokacin akan ba wa mutane labarin jarumai na wurin yaƙi da kuma farauta...”

Har wa yau, Yar’adua, (2007) da Sulaiman, (2019) sun nuna cewa: “Ana kyautata zaton cewa an fara wasan kwaikwayo ne a Kasar “Greck”, a wajen shekara dari shida kafin haihuwar Annabi Isa, Alaihissalam ne, Girkawa suka fara yin biki na waƙoƙi da raye-raye domin su girmama abin bautarsu. “Dionysis”, Ubangijinsu na giya, an ce suna wannan biki a lokaci na musamman saboda girmama da kuma neman wasu alfarma wajen wannan Ubangiji nasu. An ce shugaban wannan wasa shi ne “Thepis.”

Asali Da Samuwar Rubutaccen Wasan Kwaikwayon Hausa

Rubutaccen wasan kwaikwayon Hausa ya samo asali a sakamakon wani sauyi zamani da aka samu a rayuwar Bahausha. Wannan juyin zamanin kuwa shi ne na shigowar baƙin Turawa Kasar Hausa. Sakamakon zuwan Turawa ya haifar da samuwar rubutaccen wasan kwaikwayo da wasan kwaikwayo na gidajen rediyo da wasan kwaikwayo na majigi ko na talabijin da kuma wasan kwaikwayon finafinai.

Tsarin ilimi na Turawa ‘yan mulkin mallaka ne ya haifar da shi, duk da yake tun kafin cudanya da Turawa, Ahmed, (1987) na da ra’ayin cewa akwai wasu wasannin kwaikwayon Hausa da wani Bajamushe ya rubuta. Daga wannan ne wani Baturen Ingila ya samar da wani littafin don koya wa Hausawa yadda za su mayar da labarum su na gargajiya da tatsuniyoyinsu zuwa wasan kwaikwayo. Littafin wasan ‘*Six Hausa Plays*’ wanda aka rubuta a (1930) shi ne littafin wasan kwaikwayo da ya biyo bayan wanda Bajamushen ya rubuta, kuma Dr. R.M. East ne ya wallafa shi. A wannan littafi, East ya yi amfani ne da basirarsa ya baddalar da wasu tatsuniyoyi zuwa wasan kwaikwayo. Dalilansa na yin haka kuwa shi ne don nuna wa Hausawa wata hanya da za su sarrafa labarunsu da tatsuniyoyinsu, su rubuta wasan kwaikwayo. Daga nan sai aka sanya karatun wannan littafi cikin manhajar makaranta, dalibai na karanta shi suna aiwatar da shi a aikace. Daga nan kuma sai aka fara samun wasu dalibai masu hazaka suna rubuta nasu wasannin.

Ga wani ɗan ɓalli da Sulaiman, (2014) ya kalato na jerin wasu daga cikin litattafan wasannin kwaikwayon Hausa.

	Marubuci	Littafi	Shekara	Maɗaba’a
	R.M. East	<i>Six Hausa plays</i>	1936	Lagos.
	A.A. Tunau	<i>Wasan marafa</i>	1949	Gaskiya, Zaria.
	A.A. Dogondaji	<i>Malam Inkuntum</i>	1954	Norla, Zaria.
	A.S. Maƙarfi	<i>Zamanin Nan Namu</i>	1959	Gaskiya, Zaria.
	A.S. Maƙarfi	<i>Jatau Na Kyallu</i>	1964	Gaskiya, Zaria.
	T.W Harrison	<i>Aikin Mata</i>	1966	O.U.P.
	A. Muhd Sada	<i>Uwar Gulma</i>	1971	NNPC, Zaria

	A. Dangoggo da Dauda Kano	<i>Tabarmar Kunya</i>	1971	NNPC, Zaria
	Umar Dembo	<i>Wasannin Yara</i>	1971	NNPC, Zaria
	I.Y. Yahaya	<i>Daren sha Biyu (Fassara)</i>	1971	NNPC, Zaria
	Umaru B. Ahmed	<i>Bora da Mowa</i>	1972	NNPC, Zaria
	Bello Muh'd	<i>Malam Muhamman</i>	1974	NNPC, Zaria
	Bashari F. Roukbah	<i>Matar Mutum Kabarinsa</i>	1974	NNPC, Zaria
	Umaru Ladan da Dexter Lyndersy	<i>Shaihu Umar (Daga Kagaggen Labari)</i>	1975	NNPC, Zaria
	Ahmed Sabir	<i>Mutanen Kogo (Fassara)</i>	1976	NNPC, Zaria
	Lawal Madigawa	<i>Rayuwa</i>	1977	Kungiyar Hausa.BUK
	Hasan U	<i>Kome Nisan Jifa</i>	1978	NNPC
	Katsina U. D	<i>Kulba Na barna</i>	1979	NNPC
	Ibrahim Tajo	<i>Na-Tanko</i>	1979	Ola Printing Press Kano
	Ladan U	<i>Zaman Duniya Iyawa Ne</i>	1980	NNPC
	Idris D	<i>Matsolon Attajiri (Fassara)</i>	1981	NNPC
	Alkanci H	<i>Soyayya Ta Fi Kudi</i>	1982	NNPC
	U. Dembo	<i>Wasannin Hausa</i>	1982	Ganuwa.
	Ahmed U.B	<i>Amina Sarauniyar Zazzau</i>	1984	NNPC
	Katsina U.D	<i>Ai Ga Irin ta Nan</i>	1986	NNPC
	Yero A. K	<i>Bar Ni da Mugu</i>	1986	NNPC

	Maigari G. I	<i>Mugunta Guzurin Wuya</i>	1986	NNPC
	Sorondinki A.	<i>Gani Ga wane</i>	1990	NNPC
	Muhammad Wada Hamza	<i>Taura Biyu</i>	1993	Longman Nig Ltd
	Mahmoud Barau Bambale	<i>Kukan Kurciya</i>	1994	NNPC
	Sha'awa Ibrahim Bello Ringim	<i>Shan Koko</i>	1994	BK
	Ahmed U.B	<i>Turbar Tarabulus</i>	1999	A.B.U Press Limited.
	Ahmed U.B	<i>Tarihin Rabe</i>	1999	A.B.U Press Limited.
	Mahamoon Baba Ahmed	<i>'Yar Halas</i>	1999	Garkuwa Publication, Kaduna
	Mahamoon Baba Ahmed	<i>Makau (Fassarar Macbeth)</i>	1999	Garkuwa Publication, Kaduna
	Mahamoon Baba Ahmed	<i>Uwani Reza</i>	1999	Garkuwa Publication, Kaduna
	Mahamoon Baba Ahmed	<i>Habiba ta Habibu (Fassarar Romeo & Juliet)</i>	2000	Garkuwa Publication, Kaduna
	Ahmed U.B	<i>'Yan-matan Gaya</i>	2000	A.B.U Press Limited.
	Ahmed U.B	<i>Turbar Kudus</i>	2004	Tisman Printex Int.
	Amina Akilu Aliyu	<i>Surukan Zamani</i>	2004	G/Dabino Publishers.
	Ado Ahmed G/Dabino	<i>Malam Zalimu</i>	2009	G/Dabino Publishers.

	Bugaje Muhammad Hauwa	<i>Abin Da Kamar Wuya</i>	2009	Iqra'a Publish. House
	Ahmed U.B	<i>Gizo da Koki / Boka da Majinyaci</i>	2011	A.B.U Press Limited.
	Mahamoon Baba Ahmed	<i>Jarmai Ziza (Fassarar Julius Caesar)</i>	2012	Garkuwa Publication, Kaduna
	Faruk Mamman	<i>Tsohon Najadu</i>	2013	Famal Public. Company
	Ibrahim Waya Zara'u	<i>Kishi Ko Bata</i>	2013	Century Research Publ. Ltd Kano.
	Aminu Umar da Shehu Haladu	<i>Shugaba Mai Girma (Fassara)</i>	2014	A.B.U Press Limited.
	Khalid Imam	<i>Sodangi</i>	2014	Gidan Dabino Publishers
	Ado Ahmad Gidan Dabino	<i>Dakika Talatin</i>	2015	Gidan Dabino Publishers

Littafin Wasan Marafa

Wannan littafi na daya daga cikin litattafan farko farko da aka fara samu a fagen rubutattun wasannin kwaikwayon Hausa a shekarar (1949) da taimakon hukumar 'NORLA' wadda Gwamnatin Arewa ta kafa a (1944) don samar da littatafan adabi a harshen Hausa. Abin ban sha' awa a nan shi ne, an gina wasan ne a kan kira ga kiwon lafiyar al'ummar wancan lokacin, a kan cutar da ta kunno kai tana kai su kushewa watau cutar kurkunu da sauran makamantan cututtukan da suka addabi al'umma. Duk da yake wasu na da ra'ayin cewa an wallafa littafin ne domin a gwada takaddamar da ke tsakanin hanyoy biyu na kiwon lafiya waɗanda suke kishoyoyin juna ne, wato hanyar kiwon lafiya ta gargajiya da kuma ta zamani. Wanda ya wallafa littafin kuwa shi ne Abubakar Tunau Mafara.

Ma'anar Kiwon Lafiya

Kalmomi biyu suka haɗu suka gina kalmar 'kiwon lafiya'. Kiwo dai na nufin "(i) renon dabbobi (ii) koto (iii) lafiya watau tsabta (iv) tsawo watau hana isasshen abinci". Ita kuwa Lafiya an bayyana ta da cewa: "(i) ingancin jiki da rashin ciwo (ii) halin kirki a wurin dabbu (iii) rashin tashin hankali da hargisti a wuri", Kamusun Hausa (2006).

Har'ila yau, Kamusun (2006:256) ya ba da ma'anar Kurkunu da cewa: "cuta da ake dauka daga ruwa marar kyau; tana fitar da wani zare-zare a kafar mutum".

Dangane da irin gudummawar da masana suka ba da game da ma'anar kiwon lafiya, zamu iya kallonsa da Hanya ce da ake bi don samun ingantacin lafiya jiki da muhallin da ake rayuwa ta yau da kullum don gujewa cututtuka da ke addaban jama'a.

Zubi Da Tsari

An tsara wannan wasa ne a kan rayuwar karkara (kauye). Marubucin littafin ya tsara wasan kwaikwayonsa ya zuwa kashi biyu. A kashi na farko, ya yi kofarin bayyana matsalolin rayuwa, zamantakewar mutanen kauye, wato matsalar kazanta da iren-iren cututtuka da kazantar ke kawowa, ta dalilin amfani da kowane irin ruwa, ba tare da an tsabtace shi ba, da rashin ruwan sha mai kyau. Ga dai yadda marubucin ya kawo a gabatarwansa:

“Wannan wasa, mun shirya shi musamman don mu nuna wa jama’ a illar Kazanta. Mun yi wannan wasa a Midil ta Sakkwato sau da yawa. Kuma mun je Talatar Mafara da Gusau da Kauran Namoda duk mun yi shi a cikin 1943.

A cikin wannan dan littafi kuwa mun shirya shi ya zama kamar labari, yadda za ku iya karantawa. Amma ya fi kyau in karantawa, ku dauka a ranku kamar kuna kallon wasan ne.”

(Abubakar Tunau, 1949)

A kashi na farko ya fara siffanta gidan Marafa da rashin tsafta kamar haka:

“Wani mutumin kauye, sunansa Marafa, yana zaune a kofar dakinsa. Matansa biyu, su Kumatu da Fatse, suna cikin dakin suna kadi, ‘ya’ yansa kuma su Citumu da Mairiga da Yabini suna tare da su. Gidan Marafa ba ya da tsabta ko kadan, kaca-kaca yake. Shi Marafan kansa kuma, kurkunu ya fito masa ko’ina. Hasali dai, duk gidan Marafa babu mai isasshiyar lafiya. Daga mai kurkunu sai, mai ‘yan rani, sai mai kazwa, sai mai tari. Ko kircin jikinsu ma ya dame su.”

A nan marubucin yana kofarin siffanta irin yanayin gidan da tauraron wasan yake rayuwa a ciki da irin yadda suke zamantakewarsu da iyalinsa, haka kuma yana cikin yanayin rashin lafiya wanda kazanta da rashin tsafta ke haifar da su ga rashin tsabtataccen ruwan sha. Haka dai wasan ya ci gaba da gudana har ya kai ga rashin lafiyar ta kwantar da su, sun kasa zuwa aikin gonakinsu kamar haka:

“Kumatu: Marafa, ka ga dai zamanmu haka ba ya yiwuwa. Kada mu zama haihuwar guzuma da kwance, uwa kwance. Ga shi kai ba ka da lafiya ko kadan, kana ta fama da kurkunu, ka ma kasa yin noma. Ga mu mu ba mu da lafiya daga mu har ‘ya’yammu. Daga mai ‘yan rani sai mai kazwa, sai mai kurkunu sai mai tari. Ga shi ba ka tanada mana maganin kome ba. Ka sani kuwa kai ne shugaban gidan nan...”

Haka dai wasan ya ci gaba a wannan kashin har ya kai ga inda cutar kurkunun da zazzabi ya kama iyalan gidan Marafa suka shiga halin rashin lafiya a sanadiyar kazanta da kame-kamen wasu magungunar gargajiya da na bokaye. Wannan hujjar ce wasu ke ganin wasan Marafa na nuna taƙaddamar da ke akwai tsakanin hanyoyin magunguna na gargajiya da wafanda suke na zamani wato asibiti wanda ya samu bayan zuwan Turawan mulkin mallaka. Ga yadda aka nuna zancen Marafa da wani Boka mai tallar magungunan gargajiya kamar haka:

“Boka (ya buga tambarinsa). A sha magani ga dam-mai-ganye! A sha magani ga jikan Ladi! Maganin kwarai sai dan gado! Sai ni goga jikan Ladi! Ga maganin ki-fadi ga maganin ciwon baya, ga maganin iskoki, ga maganin kokawa, ga kuma guraye iri-iri. Yaro babu tambaya hunu ne”.

A cikin kashi na biyu kuwa marubucin wasan ya bayyana irin nasarar da aka samu wajen magance waƙannan matsalolin cututtukan da rashin tsafta ke haifarwa da yadda Marafa da iyalinsa suka samu cikakkiyar lafiya suka ci gaba da harkokinsu na yau da kullum tare da aikace-aikacensu na gona. Dukkannin nasarorin sun samu ne ta hanyar taimakon da Marafa ya samu a wajen malamin makaranta bayan ya wayar masa da kai, sannan ya rubuta masa wasika zuwa ga asibiti don samun magani.

Haka kuma wannan wasa ya yi koƙarin fito da manufar (jigon) wasan ta hanyar ilmantar da Marafa da iyalinsa, ta nusartar da su illar jahilcin da suke da shi a kan zuwa asibiti, da kuma ƙazantar da suke cikinta. Marafa ya fito a cikin wasan a kan ya jahilci aikin asibiti, lokacin da kurkunu ya fito masa, ya shiga neman magani na gargajiya da bokaye. A cikin koƙarinsa na neman magani ya sadu da malamin makaranta, wanda ya ba shi bayani da ya je asibiti inda za a yi masa magani, amma saboda jahiltar da ya yi wa asibiti, sai Marafa ya ce wa malamin:

“Ina malam? Haba malam! Yanzu ta, yaya za ka ce a kai ni asibiti? Ko don, ba ni na haife ka ba, ai na dai yi da da kai. Yaya za ka ce a kai ni inda za a cinye ni da sauran raina? Ai sai dai in, koma gida da wannan kurkunun hakanan”.

Wannan kalamai na Marafa ya nuna irin kallon da ake wa Turawan mulkin mallaka da kuma abubuwan da suka zo mana da su ƙasar Hausa. Ko shakka babu an rinka kiran Turawa ko daukarsu a matsayin dodanni, a tunanin Bahausha dai dodo cin mutane yake yi. Za mu iya tabbatar da haka idan mun yi la`akari da sunan wata unguwa da ke dab da fadar mai martaba sarkin Zazzau. Ana kiran wurin da suna 'Babban Dodo' wannan ya samo asali saboda zaman wani Baturen mulkin mallaka a wannan wurin. Wato a cikin dodannin ma, wannan Baturen babba ne. Har gobe, wannan suna 'Babban Dodo'.

Shi kuwa malamin makaranta ya dai ci gaba da fahimtar da Marafa alfanun asibiti, don ya ja hankalinsa ya je a yi masa magani, amma saboda tsabagen tunani irin na Marafa a kan asibiti, sai ma ya kara cewa malamin makaranta:

“A`a malam, na ji an ce Nasara na cin mutane”.

Daga ƙarshe dai malamin makaranta ya ciwo kan Marafa, ya amince da zuwa asibiti, amma duk da haka Marafa bai amince ba sosai, jahilcinsa na asibiti bai fita ba, sai dai kawai ya bi maganar malamin makaranta haka nan ba wai don ya gamsu ba. Ga dai abin da Marafa ya ce don duhun kansa game da asibiti:

“... Mhm. Allah Sarki! Dubi inda mutum ya, kawo kansa mahalaka. Ga ni ina ji, ina gani, da sauran ƙarfina za a halaka ni, a cinye ni, ba li ba la. Amma shi ke nan, akwai Allah.”

Bayan da Marafa, ya je asibiti, ya kware duhun tunaninsa, ya ga ainihin amfani asibiti kamar yadda malamin makaranta ya yi ta koƙarin bayyana masa, sai Marafa ya ce:

“Allah Sarki! Ka ga malam, yanzu har ga ni ina iya dan takawa da ƙarfi-ƙarfi. Ashe dai ƙarya ne da aka ce, Nasara na cin mutum.”

Haka dai Marafa ya ci gaba da bayyana wa iyalinsa cewa ba gaskiya ba ce da aka ce ana cin mutane a asibiti, wannan duk duhun jahilci ne, kansa ya waye a yanzu tun da ya je asibitin ya gani, ya kuma amfana. Ga dai ta bakin Marafa da yake cewa iyalinsa: “... Ko da aka ce suna cin mutane, wannan duk, ƙarya ne. Wannan malamin dan`uwanmu ne.”

Bayan an kore wa Marafa da iyalinsa duhun kansu game da asibiti, sai kuma Abubakar Tunau ya sake jan linzaminsa wajen fokarin ilmantar da Marafa da iyalinsa a kan yaƙi da ƙazanta, da koya masa amfanin tsabta. A nan ne, aka turo Dubagari ya zo gidan Marafa ya koya masu yadda ake yin tsafta.

Jigo:

Jigon wasan wannan shahararran littafi na wasan Marafa shi ne “Nuna fifikon asibiti domin kiwon lafiya maimakon a dogara ga hanyar neman lafiya ta gargajiya”.

Kananan Jigogi

(i) Illar rashin tsabta. (ii) Illar duhun kai (iii) Karfafa ayyukan duba gari.

Kwatanci Da Kamancin Zamanin Da Aka Rubuta Wasan Marafa Da Yau

Kamar yadda yake a wannan littafin an fara buga shi kimanin shekaru sittin da shida har ya zuwa yau. Kuma a fili yake cewa wannan littafi ya nuna al'ada da yanayi da kuma wasu camfe-camfe na malam Bahaushe, musamman a wancan lokaci. Domin kuwa wurin wannan wasa shi ne ƙasar Hausa in da Hausawa ke gudanar da rayuwarsu duk da dai in mun dubi shi Marafa mutumin karkara ne amma dai a zahiri wasu abubuwa na rashin wayewa ko kuma wasu abubuwa da dama da zamu iya hangensu a yau a matsayin rashin ci gaba ko kuma rashin wayewar kai.

Bangare guda kuma a akwai wasu abubuwa da dama da Abubakar Tunau ya kawo su a wancan lokacin wafanda in muka kalli wannan zamanin da muke ciki, za mu fahimci a yau ci gaba aka samu.

(i) Raguwar Camfe-cmfe da tasirinsu ga Al'umma.

(ii) Daukan ciwo ko cuta a matsayin hanyar ajali.

(iii) Karfafa ayyukan malaman tsabta.

(iv) Muhimmancin malamin makaranta da irin rawar da yake takawa ga ci gaban rayuwar al'umma.

(v) Dogaro da kai ta hanyar noma tukuru.

(vi) Inganta asibitoci da dakunan shan magani.

Shawarwari

Gwamnatoƙin Nijeriya ko ta Karamar Hukuma ce ko ta Jiha ko Tarayya ce su kasance suna ma fannin kiwon lafiya kula ta musamman wajen tafiyar da jama'arsu don haka shawararmu ga mabiya ita ce kamar haka:

- Tsaftace muhallanmu a kowane lokaci.
- Kula da sharrudan ma'aikatan dubagari.
- Neman Ilmi a kan tsarin tsaftace muhalli ga malaman makaranta.
- Neman Ilmi daga kafafen yada labarai a kan muhimmancin tsaftace muhalli.
- Kira ga ƙungiyoyin marubuta, da su riƙa rubuta wasa da ya shafi wannan ɓangaren na kiwon lafiya, da kuma tsaftar muhalli.
- Kira ga hukumomin lafiya da su inganta ayyukansu na kula da muhalli.
- Kira ga gwamnati da ta duba ta kuma ya nazari a game da ayyukan duba-gari, don tabbatar da jama'a na kula da tsabtar muhalli da ta jiki, don kiwon lafiya ta inganta, saboda masu iya magana sun ce: “Lafiya uwar jiki.”

Kammalawa.

A farko wannan takarda an ga irin gudummuwar masana game da ma'anar wasan kwaikwayo da yadda aka fara samun rubutattun wasannin kwaikwayo a kasar Hausa cikin harshen Hausa sai kuma irin nasarar da aka samu a fagen adabi, a fagen kamfanoni madaba'an littattafan adabi da na gasa. Kuma takardar ta yi nazarin ma'anar kiwon lafiya da irin cutar da marubucin ya mayar da akalarsa a kai, watau cutar kurkunu da mashasharan zazzabi. Baya ga haka a tasirin zamani a yau cigaban da aka samu game da kiwon lafiya

An sami canji da ci gaba ta bangaren kiwon lafiya, ta rage yaduwar cututtuka a birni da karkara, sakamakon ci gaban rayuwa ta bangaren yaduwar ilimin zamani. Mutanen zamani a yanzu sun fahimci illa kazanta da zama cikin kazantar. Haka kuma ci gaban da aka samu ta fannin sadarwa, ta kafafen fasahar zamani kamar rediyo ta talbijin da kafafen sada zumunta suna taimakawa wajen wayar da kan jama'a don kula da lafiya da muhalli. A sakamakon haka, an samu bacewar wadansu cututtuka da suka addabi mutane harma sukan yi kisa, kamarsu: agana ('yan rani) da ciwon maibushe (kwalaria) da atuni (kurga) da bakon dauro da kazzuwa da kurkunu da sauransu.

Haka nan kuma an sake samun ci gaba ta fanni daban-daban a fagen kiwon lafiya da tsaftace muhalli ta sanadiyyar ayyukan wadannan kafafen yada labaru, idan wata sabuwar cutar ta bullo, kamar irinsu kanjamau da ciwon siga da hawan jini. Sai dai kash! A fagen rubutattun wasannin kwaikwayo an sami nakasu, wajen samun irin wadannan rubutattun wasanni da suke kira a kan kiwon lafiya da kula da tsafar muhalli da suka shafi ire-iren wadannan sabbin cututtuka, saboda ilmantarwa cikin nishadi game da illolin da ke tattare da wadannan cutuka, da kuma samar ma dalibai hanyar nazari da bincike ta bangaren rubutattun wasannin kwaikwayo. Wadanda aka fi samu su ne a wasannin kwaikwayo na Rediyo ko na Talbijin. Wannan ma wani ci gaba ne wanda mai bincike yake ganin za a iya fadada bincike akai.

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